

Why was the Estates General was not able to deal with the issues France faced

The Estates General was not able to deal with the issues that France faced because a range of political, social and economic factors such as creeping bankruptcy; political instability, and urge for change; and dissatisfaction with the class inequality that led to resistance that dismantled the function of the Estates General. King Louis XVI followed the advice of the Controller General of Finances of the time, Necker, in calling the Estate General to help reduce government spending and increase the tax rate to provide a bigger surplus to pay off the loans that France was dependent on.

There was large uncertainty around this decision as the Estate General hasn't met for 175 years and only met when the country was facing a large crisis like a war disease outbreak. Due to this large gap nobody was really certain how the conference should proceed. The Estate General was represented by three Estates, consisting of the Clergy, Nobility and a very large III Estate that consisted of Middle class, peasants, working class and all other classes of society. Even though the Third Estate Represented the Large majority of the population (Around 98%) each estate had one vote meaning the clergy and nobility had an upper hand in the decision-making process which greatly frustrated the Third Estate that resisted so king was forced to allow 600 member of the Third Estate to be present while Nobility and Clergy has 300 each. However their vote was still underrepresented which largely contributed to the inability of Estate General to deal with the issues in France. Therefore large number of members in the assembly were conspiring against the assembly itself which led to the Estate General not being able to solve the problems that France had.

Cahiers were books that the king requested in January of 1789 that each representative of Estate General brings to the session. They contained public grievances and suggestions, and raised expectations that the Estate General would bring about a fundamental overhaul of France. However it was over optimistic as the structure of the Ancien regime could never meet the expectations. Finance was a major issue facing France, but the cahiers were contradictory in the solutions they proposed, as there had been no royal direction in their production, and this fed through to the early debates. This meant that people largely overestimated the work of the General while it wasn't even in the interest of the assembly to discuss the main problems that France faced which meant it was not able to deal with the issues France had.

The biggest problem the Estate General Faced was massive government spending such as the American War of Independence made France be fully dependent on Foreign loans so it was expected that the Estate General would redistribute the tax and move some of the tax burdens on the first and the second Estate as at that point only Third Estate was paying tax and they were fed up with the likes of the salt tax. However, since the first two estates had the voting majority and the King was aware that no change and issue-solving could be dealt with in terms of more even taxation. In the Eyes of Necker “The King did not summon the Estates because he needed them, but out of his own pleasure.” which brought growing hatred from all classes that dismantled the works of the Estate General. When Necker resigned due to pressure from conservative ministers Maurepas and Vergennes for his publishing of the court's balance sheet the public outcry became even larger. Therefore because the groups that were the root cause of the overspending were the ruling class in the Estate General it was unable and unwilling to deal with the main problem of France.

Louis XVI sought to keep the Estates General's voting bias which discriminated against the Third Estate. In response it challenged the king's power when it voted to call itself the National Assembly and claimed it had the right to decide on matters of taxation. This had never been a reason for the calling of the Estates General. When the third Estate and some members from the other two Estates broke off from the Estate General in order to form a National assembly they were stopped from assembling by the king so they moved to a tennis court in Versailles and promised the Tennis court oath which stated the newly formed assembly will be in session until a constitution for France is drafted. This ultimately stopped the Estate General from meeting and discussing any of the prevalent problems. The assembly became aggressive and refused to disband as was stated by the Honore Mirabeau in June 1789: “If you have been instructed to make us leave this place, you should seek permission to use force, for only the power of bayonets will dislodge us”. And the king's response was simply “Ah f–k it, let them stay.” This resistance from the core groups of the Estate General and the unwillingness of the king to meet their demands meant that the core structure of the general was broken so it was fully dismantled in operating and solving the issues that the country faced.

Whilst the new National Assembly was becoming more strident, the fear grew, which was not unfounded, that Louis XVI was seeking to deploy additional troops in Paris to restore his authority. This led to disorder, in the cities and the countryside such as the storming of the Bastille. French Writer Louis-Sebastian Mercier describes the events as “In two minutes the work of centuries was overturned. Palaces and houses destroyed, churches overturned, their vaults torn asunder.” The Estate General due to the formation of the National Constituent Assembly had to have been dismantled prematurely on the 9th of July meaning it could no longer deal with any issues of France before proposing any solutions. Using the Estates General, an old institution of the Ancien Regime had shown that the issues France faced could only be dealt with by new institutions based on new ideas. All social, economic and political factors were working against

the dealings of the Estate General and its existence was fundamentally doomed to fail. This meant because the assembly had to deal with so many internal pressures it was unable to deal with the problems facing the country.